

An Insight on Consumer’s Hedonic Behavior, Attitude and Purchase Intention towards the Counterfeit fashion Products

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ABSTRACT

Counterfeiting is a major and an emergent problem globally, growing both in developed and developing countries. Counterfeiting is also a most important issue for companies, public institutions and consumers. The product of counterfeiting is not a new occurrence but the put into practice have a gigantic development in the last three decades and at the moment it is growing at a more rapidly than ever it before. It is affected almost all industries. eg. apparels, food, cosmetics, electrical, electronic, softwares, etc. The pace of globalization and technological development enhance the growth of these illegal players to enter any market in the world with high technological sophistication. The consumers' involvement in the process is an important factor to enhance the growth especially in non deceptive counterfeiting. There are only limited studies are available on the role of hedonic behavior in the non deceptive counterfeiting and no studies are available among Indian consumers. This paper is one of the few studies to investigate the role of hedonic factor towards the attitude and purchase intention on counterfeited market product with trying to identify the demographic differences in the three behavioral variables. The questionnaire was designed based on established scales adopted from past studies and administered to buyers in the market. The reliability of the construct is tested by using the Cronbach alpha test and the structural model and hypothesis are tested by using Partial Least Squares (PLS). Anova and t test are used to understand the profile differences of the customers.

The PLS results shows the significant and positive direct relationship between the purchase intention and hedonic behavior. There is a further scope for research on brand specific studies in order to get the mere behavior of the consumer's for the strategic decision making of the specific brand.

1. Introduction

Counterfeiting is a major and an emergent problem globally, growing both in developed and developing countries. Counterfeiting is also a most important issue for companies, public institutions and consumers. The product of counterfeiting is not a new occurrence but the put into practice have a gigantic development in the last three decades and at the moment it is growing at a more rapidly than ever it before (Bian, 2016). The authentic producers, administration and other national and international agencies are dedicating massive investment to deal with this problem. Majority of the markets now are flooded with diverse counterfeit products such as clothing, wallets, handbags, perfumes, sun glasses, books, auto parts, toys, camera, food and beverages, tobacco, personal care products, shoes, watches, leather goods, and jewelry due to continuous demand from consumers. The fashion product industry is one of the most worthwhile area in the business world and having high growth rate in the market, But this is one among the most affected industry in the list of most counterfeited areas (Vinita Bhatia, 2018). Counterfeit product can be defined as “Counterfeit trademark goods shall mean any goods, including packaging, bearing without authorization a trademark which is identical to the trademark validly registered in respect of such goods, or which cannot be distinguished in its essential aspects from such a trademark and which thereby infringes the rights of the owner of the trademark in question under the law of the country of

importation” (Kumar, R et al., 2015) The consumption of counterfeit product is increasing day by day in the world. The government and other agencies are focused only on the supply side of the counterfeit products. Apart from the value of the products there are some factors which are influencing the consumer behavior towards the counterfeit products.

This paper is one of the few studies to investigate the role of hedonic factor towards the attitude and purchase intention on counterfeited market product with try to identify the demographic differences in the three behavioral variables. Apart from the socio economic factors the past studies are lacking the unethical aspects in the counterfeiting. In order to curb demand for counterfeit products would require an understanding as to what motivates a buyer to willingly buy a counterfeit product.

2. The study hypothesis and Literature Review

The purchase behavior of the customer is highly influenced by the behavioral intention of the customer and the behavioral intention is influenced by the attitude towards the product (Vinita Bhatia, 2018). The theory of planned behavior and theory of reasoned action is the purchasing behaviors of the customers are influenced by the purchase intention, the purchase intention is determined by the customer's attitude towards the product. As such, the following hypothesis is proposed.

H1- The customer’s attitude towards the counterfeited of fashion product is positively related by the intention to purchase counterfeit of fashion product.

Apart from the utilitarian needs there are some hedonic advantages which are attracting the customer’s preference on the counterfeit products. Such as, the brand name, label, trademark and other identifying characteristics are the product, like product logo, pattern, colour etc (Rahman, A.,et.al.2016;Babin,et.al.1994).Counterfeits products are the better, improved and low-cost choices as soon as consumers are looking for hedonic benefits rather than some pragmatic requirements; they are less concerned with quality of counterfeits. Style and design of counterfeits both substances for consumers at the time of buy choice. There for the following hypothesis is proposed.

H2-Hedonic behavioral values have a positive influence on the customer’s attitude towards the counterfeit products.

H3-Hedonic behavioral values have a positive influence on purchase intention

Counterfeiting is term used to refer to any product which so such as an imitates that of other as to mislead a consumer that it is the product of that other, include the unauthorized production and distribution of a product that is protects by other intellectual property right, such as copyright. Other defined of Brand product Counterfeiting is as the copies of original product and brands such as packaging, logos, or similar with attributes

of original. Counterfeit consumption is the “unauthorized reproduction of goods protected by an intellectual property right” (T,Ashtray,2011). This is a growing phenomenon, as 59% to 70% of the North American populations have engaged in this behavior (Nia & Zaichkowsky, 2000; Walthers & Buff, 2008).Counterfeiting has a significant impact on the various stake holders like legitimate producers, consumers, government, brand owners and the society as whole. (Bian, 2016). There are lot of studies find out that, people who are earning lower income are more intended to purchase the counterfeit products than people who are earning more (Ang et al., 2001; Tan, 2002; Kempen, 2003; Franses and Lede, 2012; Hamelin et al., 2013; Stravinskiene et al., 2013; Stephen et al., 2014; Vinita Bhatia,2017).

3. Methodology

The questionnaire was designed based on established scales adopted from past studies and administered to buyers in the market. Totally 102 respondents were selected for analysis after removing the uncompleted responses and unengaged responses. The reliability of the construct is tested by using the Cronbach alpha test and the structural model and hypothesis are tested by using Partial Least Squares (PLS). Anova and t test are used to understand the profile differences of the customers.

Table 1: The construct formation details

Construct	Number of measuring Items	Source
Attitude Towards Counterfeited Product	5	Matos et.al.(2007);Huang et.al.(2014);Mao Seng Ting et.al.(2016)
Purchase Intention	5	Matos et.al.(2007);Zeithaml et.al.(1996);Mao Seng Ting et.al.(2016)
Hedonistic Behavior	4	Kaufmann, H. R et.al.(2016)

All the items are adopted from the given sources of past studies.

4. Empirical results and discussion

Table 2: ANOVA and t test analysis result for the difference between demographic variable to the variable ‘Hedonic Behavior’

Variable	Categories	N	Mean	One way ANOVA and t test Results	
				F/t Value	Sig. level
Gender	Male	42	2.93	.222	.639
	Female	60	2.99		
Age	15-20	14	2.81	.947	.391
	21-26	69	3.04		
	27-35	16	2.77		
	36-45	3	2.80		

Variable	Categories	N	Mean	One way ANOVA and t test Results	
				F/t Value	Sig. level
Education	SSLC or Less	2	3.60	1.323	.267
	HSS	5	3.20		
	UG	20	2.82		
	PG	52	3.02		
	Ph.D.	23	2.85		

Occupation	Student	89	2.93	.601	.699
	Unemployed	1	3.40		
	Employed for Wages	6	2.93		
	Govt.employee	2	3.20		
	Self employed	2	3.40		
	Others	2	3.40		
Income	Not Applicable	59	2.91	.422	.832
	10000 or Less	15	3.02		
	10001 to 20000	7	3.20		
	20001 to 35000	18	3.00		
	35001 and above	3	2.87		
Religion	Hindu	45	3.160	1.762	.115
	Muslim	10	3.160		
	Christian	30	2.827		
	No religion	8	3.100		
	Others	9	2.445		

After the ANOVA and t test to check the difference of preference, there is no significant difference between customer's demographic profiles (Gender, Age, Education,

Occupation, Income and Religion) to the hedonic behavior of the customer towards the counterfeit of fashion product.

Table 3: ANOVA and t test analysis result for the difference between demographic variable to the variable 'attitude towards the product'

Variable	Categories	N	Mean	One way ANOVA and t test Results	
				F/t Value	Sig. level
Gender	Male	42	2.70	.00	1.00
	Female	60	2.70		
Age	15-20	14	2.51	1.83	.166
	21-26	69	2.76		
	27-35	16	2.55		
	36-45	3	3.00		
Education	SSLC or Less	2	3.5	3.365	.013*
	HSS	5	2.4		
	UG	20	2.72		
	PG	52	2.85		
	Ph.D.	23	2.33		
Occupation	Student	89	2.73	1.265	.286
	Unemployed	1	1		
	Employed for Wages	6	2.56		
	Govt.employee	2	2.60		
	Self employed	2	2.70		
	Others	2	2.70		
Income	Not Applicable	59	2.71	2.017	.083
	10000 or Less	15	2.49		
	10001 to 20000	7	3.05		
	20001 to 35000	18	2.77		
	35001 and above	3	2.20		
Religion	Hindu	45	2.75	.762	.601
	Muslim	10	2.72		
	Christian	30	2.59		
	No religion	8	2.97		
	Others	9	2.53		

With the exception of education of the customers all other demographic characteristics don't have any significance difference in attitude towards the counterfeit product. The post hoc result says there is a difference in attitude towards the

counterfeit product among the SSLC(2.33) and Ph.D.(3.50).Even though the results gives a difference in attitude the number of respondents who are having SSLC education is only 2.

Table 4: ANOVA and t test analysis result for the difference between demographic variable to the variable 'Purchase Intention'

Variable	Categories	N	One way ANOVA and t test Results	
			F/t Value	Sig. level

Gender	Male	42	2.65	.040	.841
	Female	60	2.62		
Age	15-20	14	2.54	2.491	.088
	21-26	69	2.67		
	27-35	16	2.56		
	36-45	3	2.66		
Education	SSLC or Less	2	3.75	2.094	.087
	HSS	5	2.55		
	UG	20	2.58		
	PG	52	2.68		
	Ph.D.	23	2.47		
Occupation	Student	89	2.62	1.313	.265
	Unemployed	1	1.50		
	Employed for Wages	6	2.77		
	Govt.employee	2	2.75		
	Self employed	2	2.37		
	Others	2	3.37		

Variable	Categories	One way ANOVA and t test Results			
		N		F/t Value	Sig. level
Income	Not Applicable	59	2.61	1.035	.402
	10000 or Less	15	2.61		
	10001 to 20000	7	2.64		
	20001 to 35000	18	2.77		
	35001 and above	3	2.25		
Religion	Hindu	45	3.16	.967	.452
	Muslim	10	3.16		
	Christian	30	2.827		
	No religion	8	3.100		
	Others	9	2.445		

There is no significant difference in between customer’s demographic profiles (Gender, Age, Education, Occupation, Income and Religion) towards the purchase intention of the counterfeit of fashion product.

A measurement model is constructed by using smart PLS in order to find out the influence of hedonic behavior on purchase intention directly as well as indirectly through attitude towards the counterfeit product. The reliability of factors in the model is

confirmed by using factor loadings for each of the item in the construct. In the initial path model we had four items are to measure hedonic behavior, five items are to measure attitude towards the product and purchase intention. After considering the general criteria for retention of items in the construct (factor loading more than 0.5 are retained) some of the items are dropped. In the final path model, factor loadings of all items are above 0.5. This confirms the reliability of the constructs in the final model.

Table 5: Factor loadings, Cronbach's alpha, composite reliability and AVE

	Factor loadings	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	AVE
Hedonic Behavior		0.8093	0.8701	0.6290
HED-2	.859			
HED-3	.778			
HED-4	.727			
Attitude towards the Product		0.70	0.8320	0.6238
ATP-2	.678			
ATP-3	.881			
ATP-4	.721			
ATP-5	.872			
Purchase Intention		0.8477	0.8313	0.6213
PI-1	.793			
PI-2	.800			
PI-3	.736			
PI-4	.803			
PI-5	.808			

Convergent Validity

The degree of agreement in two or more measures of the same construct is assessed by Convergent validity. It is assessed by variance extracted for each factor. As per the

criteria it should be more than 0.5. The results are indicated that it is ranged from 0.678 to 0.881. This confirms the scale used for measuring hedonic behavior, attitude towards the product and purchase intention possess the convergent validity.

Table 6: Showing the Discriminant Validity Results

	ATP	HED	PI
ATP	0.793		
HED	0.3321	0.790	
PI	0.3126	0.5098	0.788

Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity shows the degree to which is a single construct is different from the remaining constructs in the overall model. The discriminant validity will be adequate if the construct have the AVE value greater than 0.5. This means 50% of the

measurement variance is captured by the construct. Since the diagonal values in the table are greater than the off diagonal values, the constructs in the model possess discriminant validity.

Figure 1: Final Structural Equation Model

Figure 2: Showing the path coefficients along with their bootstrap values, 'T' values

Path coefficients suggest that there is a positive relationship between the hedonic behavior to the purchase intention (Beta= 0.456, t value=3.733) and there is a positive relationship between the hedonic behavior to the Purchase Intention (Beta= 0.332, t value=3.805). The results also suggest that the

indirect relationship between hedonic behavior and purchase intention through attitude towards the product is insignificant. This indicates the mediating role of attitude towards the product in the relationship between hedonic behavior and purchase intention is not significant.

Table 7: Showing the path coefficients along with their bootstrap values, 'T' values

Path	Original Sample (O)	Sample Mean (M)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	Standard Error (STERR)	T Statistics (O/STERR)
HED -> ATP	0.3321	0.3479	0.0844	0.0844	3.9345
ATP -> PI	0.1610	0.1746	0.0979	0.0979	1.6450
HED -> PI	0.4563	0.4596	0.1242	0.1242	3.6738

From the three paths in the measures which are connecting in the structural model, The HED -> PI hypotheses is supported. This implies that hedonic behaviors of the customers are positively influencing the purchase intention of the counterfeited branded product. The hypothesis HED -> ATP is supported. This implies that hedonic behaviors of the customers are positively influencing the attitude of the customers towards the counterfeited branded product. The result is also suggests that the indirect relationship between hedonic behavior and purchase intention through attitude towards the product is insignificant.

5. Conclusion and implications for theory and practice

This study gives a significant role of hedonic behavioral role of customer's attitude towards the purchase intention of the counterfeit of fashion product in the market. The PLS results

shows the significant and positive direct relationship between the purchase intention and hedonic behavior.

From a managerial perspective, the findings from this research may help marketing practitioners and policy makers alike to establish more refined, effective, and actionable counter strategies.

This study has some limitations, the study focused only on one of the influencing aspect of the customer's towards the purchase intention of the counterfeited products. There are other factors like motivational as well as socio economic factors on attitude and purchase intention towards the counterfeit products. There is a further scope for research on brand specific studies in order to get the mere behavior of the consumer's for the strategic decision making of the specific brand.

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